

ASSESSMENT OF POSITIVE PARENTING STYLE AND DIMENSIONS AMONG PARENTS OF PRIMARY CHILDREN USING NICOMACHUS-POSITIVE PARENTING (NPP) QUESTIONNAIRE

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History Received: October 31, 2021 Accepted: December 20, 2021</p> <p>Keywords positive psychology, parenting style; social issues; reliability; validity..</p> <p>DOI: 10.5480/zenodo.5015487</p> <p>(ISSN:1068-3844)</p>	<p><i>The aim of the present study is to adapt Nicomachus-Positive Parenting (NPP) Questionnaire to the parents of primary children ages between 7 to 13 years. The original scale was proposed by Seligman in Authentic Happiness. The data were collected from 100 respondents in India, Chennai to check the validity and reliability of the testing of questionnaire. The samples were chosen using simple random sampling method and uses descriptive research method of survey. The Cronbach coefficient(a) was evaluated for each sub-study. The objective of this research is to discover the various dimensions of positive psychology parenting style such as nurturing values (0.739), strength identification and boosting (0.727), parenting context (0.705), and involvement (0.679) in parenting approach toward the child and parental attitudes. The attitude of parents directly linked with child internalization, externalization, and social issues. The parent may provide a pleasant environment for the children, the parent's behaviour may alter, positively or negatively impacting the child's development. It shapes and feeds them from infancy to adulthood. We must give our children a sense of belonging and security. It investigates the consequences of parenting styles and their impact on children. Parents' personal information were also collected in order to see if there was a link between their attitudes and behaviour based on social dimension of parenting, and the data was evaluated using statistical analysis. Though the percentage of dimensions of parenting were high and showing nurturing values (82%), strength identification and boosting (86%), parenting context (92%), and involvement (92%) but the coefficient values were less as compared to the percentage values. Even though the values are high, coefficient values are less, it clearly shows that the parent involvement is very important in bringing up the child and should concentrate more on that and parent should be engaged in counselling and they should be prepared to accept their child as they are.</i></p>

Introduction

Parenting is an important predictor of children's social and emotional adjustment(Maccoby, 2000)(Cowan, 2004). It is an art of nurturing the values among children. Parents attitudes and emotions during the ages of 7 to 13 years children have a great impact on their children behaviour. Children's behaviour and disciplinary attitudes depends on what they perceive from their parents. Parenting is not just about promoting a child's physical development; it is also about encouraging their cerebral development (Jinnah & Walters, 2003). Parents unquestionably have the biggest influence on their character of the children development and how successful they are in life as they become older. The life children are not complete without their families. It molds and nourishes them from an young age into adults. Give your children a sense of family and explain to them why it is essential. If you do so, your children are more likely to grow up respecting and loving their family no matter what. The study is significant that many children commit suicide for their small failures, attempt to suicide or become pervert and divert to antisocial activities. Asian continent observes these incidents growing

exponentially. There are different types of parental behaviour dimensions in contemporary parenting style: nurturing values, strength identification and boosting, parenting context and involvement.

Positive psychology: Martin Seligman, a psychologist, is widely recognized with developing Positive Psychology, which is based on his work. It entails scientific research into ideas, feelings, and behaviours that focuses on strengths rather than flaws and looks for methods to improve our mental well-being (Kyriazos & Stalikas, 2019).

Positive Parenting: Positive parenting aims to bring out the best in our children by highlighting their assets. Positive behaviours are celebrated and encouraged rather than bad ones are aggressively sought to be prevented. Positive parenthood is a loving and kind approach to parenthood that promotes healthy parent-child relationships. Some skills can be used by parents to make positive parents, including validation, balance, listening and support.

In 2002, Seligman, meticulously described a model of parenting effectiveness, based on the principles of Positive Psychology. Despite that, to the best of our knowledge, this parenting model received less attention than the rest of the Authentic Happiness model components (Mohammad et al., n.d.). To hopefully promote research in this area, a first step would be developing a new measure of Positive Psychology parenting, operationalizing this Authentic Happiness parenting model. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to describe the development and validation of a new measure of Positive Psychology Parenting (Nicomachus Positive Parenting or NPP)(Kyriazos & Stalikas, 2019).

Good Parenting Style: Good parenting is a basis for better social and academic skills and it involves healthy parent involvement and intervention in children's day-to-day lives. A secure attachment leads to a healthy development of society, emotions, cognition and motivation. We can go far into how effective parenting is in preparing the children for social interaction. It is a fact that child development may be positive or negative effect on their academic, mental, behavioural and social conduct depends on their parental behaviour (Joseph & John, 2008).

Nurturing Values: Values are significant in parenting and they have a profound impact on our attitudes and behaviours, as well as our decisions and interpersonal relationships. To fully embrace a value, you must act on it and your conduct must reflect it, not merely accept it verbally or believe you should follow it. Young children pick up family values from their parents and other family members. You will be able to see your family's values reflected in your child's surroundings if they involve sharing, communicating and mutual respect (Kiff et al., 2011).

Strength Identification & Boosting: When parents adopt a strength-based approach, they seek to deliberately identify and cultivate positive states, positive processes and positive qualities in their children (Waters, 2015). Nothing makes a parent happier than watching their child happy. Inspiring moments include seeing the pride in their eyes as they accomplish a chore, hearing them laugh at a joke, or seeing them smile as they proudly give over their newest artistic creation. Learning to identify your kid's strengths and working with them is an important part of strength-based parenting since it prepares your child up for future success while also having fun.

Parenting Context: Parenting context play a role in shaping the expression of temperament. may be more or less accepting or accommodating of the child's characteristic responses (Rothbart et al., 2001). Thus, temperament represents characteristics present early in life that shape and are shaped within the context of social and environmental interactions and that result in differential responsiveness to socialization experiences (Shiner & Caspi, 2003). Many aspects of a child's growth and development are influenced by their surroundings. Emotional development is influenced by a variety of factors,

including the children's biological family, schools, communities, and culture. There has been research showing that when parents display good emotions, their children are more likely to engage in prosocial conduct, social competence, and positive emotionality.

Involvement: Parental involvement is essential for a child's entire development, and it has a beneficial effect. It gives parents the ability to see their children's strengths and weaknesses (Önder & Gülay, 2009).

The objective of this research article is to conduct a survey through a NPP questionnaire on among primary school parents to check its reliability, internal consistency and validity. Further to draw conclusions pertaining to social and psychological dimensions of positive parenting.

Literature Review

Many negative parenting behaviors predict increases in frustration, fearfulness, and control. Irritability renders children more susceptible to negative parenting behaviors. Fearfulness operates in a very complex manner, sometimes increasing children's responses to parenting behaviors and sometimes mitigating them and apparently operating differently across gender. Important directions for future research include the use of study designs and analytic approaches that account for the direction of effects and for developmental changes in parenting and temperament over time (Cowan, 2004). Uninvolved parenting styles rank lowest across all life domains. These children tend to lack self-control, have low self-esteem and are less competent than their peers. Children develop best when they have love and limits. If they are neglected and given a little guidance, they won't learn self-control and may become quite selfish, unruly and lacking in direction. And if they receive too much guidance, as the children of authoritarian parents do, they will have few opportunities to learn self-reliance and may lack confidence in their own decision-making abilities. In today's complex world, men and women are not ascertained about how to rear children as they were in previous generations. Clarifying parenting values and implementing them in warm, supportive and appropriately demanding ways are crucial for the welfare of the next generation and society (Joseph & John, 2008). School climate includes positive attitudes of the school staff toward the community, attention to details that facilitate parental accessibility to the school (such as interpreter availability and scheduling school meetings), physical space to accommodate parents and families, and support and encouragement for personal contact and communication. An alienating environment is, for most children, exacerbated if school personnel and teachers do not speak to the parent's native language and if translators are unavailable for meetings (Arias & Morillo-Campbell, 2008).

Method

The research is a survey for scale adaptation to measure the reliability and validity of NPP Questionnaire. The sample consists of 100 parents of primary age group children (7-13 years) in India, Chennai. The demographic variables are also collected from the respondents in terms of profession, type of family, parent category, socio-economic status, parent's educational qualification and monthly income. NPP Questionnaire was used as an instrument in this research article. Personal information of parents was also collected for the purpose of finding the association between the attitudes and behaviour based on their demographic and social variables as mentioned above. We have selected four positive parenting factors such as nurturing values, strength identification & boosting, parenting context and

involvement proposed by Seligman in Authentic Happiness (Önder & Gülay, 2009) included four factors consists of 20 items, which assesses the positive psychology of parenting behaviour. The parents required to respond on the five point Likert scale described as, 1 = absolutely untrue; 2 = mostly untrue; 3 = can't say true or untrue; 4 = mostly true; 5 = absolutely true (Kyriazos & Stalikas, 2019). The score was five to one. There are no negative items. Scores for each parent were taken separately and sum of scores of each parents were taken for overall score of an item (Gafoor & Kurukkan, 2014). Personal information was collected from the parents of primary age group children of age 7 to 13. Respondents were informed in prior about research procedure before they started to response to the items.

Analysis of Data

The collected data were analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The scale which was developed for this research for its reliability is Cronbach Alpha method. Itemwise analysis were made for the criteria of validity.

Results

1. Scale Reliability: Internal Consistency Coefficients

Internal reliability of the scale of NPP Questionnaire was tested with the techniques of Cronbach alpha method. According to this test, it is found to be relatively high. It is high because it clearly states that parental influences have more impact on child in all the dimensions of parenting style. This illustrates only the positive side of the coin. But it is not same for the all the situations. As the situations may get worsen at times, then that time the behaviours of the children may vary. They may not behave as they behaved earlier. The parent may give plenty of decent surroundings but one worst situation of the parent may change the behaviour and that may have adverse effect on the development of the child.

2. Results of Nicomachus-Positive Parenting Questionnaire:

Table 1: Dimension 1: Nurturing Values

Items	Mean	SD	Pct.	
Dimension 1: Nurturing Values				
Q1	I encourage my child to keep his/her sense of humour even in hard times	3.850	1.1367	77%
Q2	I encourage my child to fight for what is fair	4.300	.6569	86%
Q3	I incite my child to always tell the truth	4.050	.8870	81%
Q4	I urge on my child to retry things, he/she wasn't successful in the past	3.800	1.4726	76%
Q5	I incite my child to be enthusiastic with everything he/she does	4.600	0.8208	92%
Q6	I urge my child on reading books	4.200	0.7678	84%
Q7	I encourage my child to do the right thing, even when there is no personal gain	3.900	0.8522	78%
Q8	I encourage my child to motivate and support others when he/she participates in group activities	4.150	0.8751	83%
Q9	I urge my child on giving a second chance to other people	4.150	0.8751	83%

Figure 1: Dimension 1: Nurturing Values

Table 1: Analysis & Interpretation of Nurturing Values

Nurturing values dimension discusses about the parental values and their relationship with their children in their activities. Item 5 has the highest percentage of 92% which reveals that most of the parent’s attitudes are extremely motivating their children in whatever the things they do. There are about five items no. 2,3,6,8 and 9 ranges between 81%-86% shows that the parent’s attitude in nurturing values are highly encouraging among their children to fight for what is fair, insist them to tell truth, reading books and supporting group activities. There are about three items no. 1,4 and 7 ranges between 76%-78% shows that the parent’s attitude is moderately low in encouraging their children when they are emotionally down. And they are not urging them to try things even if they fail after multiple attempts and not insisting them to follow the right direction even if there is no personal gain.

Table 2: Dimension 2: Strength Identification & Boosting

Items	Mean	SD	Pct.	
Dimension 2: Strength Identification & Boosting				
Q10	I am in readiness to see into my child’s strengths	4.350	0.7452	87%
Q11	Some of my child’s strengths stand out more clearly than others	4.400	0.7539	88%
Q12	I can say I am sufficiently aware of my child’s strengths	4.600	0.8826	92%
Q13	I encourage my child to study something related to his/her character strengths	3.850	0.8751	77%
Q14	I make sure that my child’s extracurricular activities cultivate his/her character strengths	4.400	0.8826	88%

Figure 2: Dimension 2: Strength Identification & Boosting

Table 2: Analysis & Interpretation of Strength Identification & Boosting

Strength Identification & Boosting dimension discusses about the identifying strength and improving their character. Item 12 has the highest percentage of 92%, which reveals that most of the

parents are adequately aware of their child's strength. There are about three items no. 10,11 and 14 ranges between 87%-88% shows that the parent's attitude towards strength identification and boosting are highly encouraging and reveals that they are keen in identifying their child's strength, which in turns makes their child stand out clearly in their path by involving them in extracurricular activities to cultivate their strength. Item no. 13 has the lowest percentage of 77%, which indicates that the parents are not encouraging their children to study or involve in activities which they are interested in and children are forced to do the activities which the parents like.

Table 3: Dimension 3: Parenting Context

Items	Mean	SD	Pct.	
Dimension 3: Parenting Context				
Q15	I do not have problems with my marriage or personal relationship	4.500	0.7609	90%
Q16	I have a good relationship with my extended family members	4.700	0.6569	94%
Q17	My husband/partner supports me when I need it	4.600	0.6806	92%

Figure 3: Dimension 3: Parenting Context

Table 3: Analysis & Interpretation of Parenting Context

Parenting Context dimension discusses about the shaping behaviours of their children based on their relationship with them and their family members. Item 15-16 have high percentage between 90% to 94% which reveals that most of the parents are having positive relationship with their children and their family members. They do not have any conflicts among them, hence the children are nurtured in a positive way. Though the reliability is highly good we cannot assume that it does not need much focus. The percentage lags matter a lot. Parents behaviours may not be same at all the times. Parents are in compulsion to maintain their positive standards, since the children have not faced any consequences in a family relationship. But it is impossible for many of the parents to maintain it. Because there may be difference of opinions between the partners, within the family. These may lead to quarrel between them which affects the child psychology. Children are likely to be more sensitive and the bad things are easily creating an impact and tends unbalancing emotions.

Table 4: Dimension 4: Involvement

Items	Mean	SD	Pct.	
Dimension 3: Involvement				
Q18	I help my child do his/her homework	4.600	0.7539	92%
Q19	I get my child to his/her extracurricular activities	4.550	0.6863	91%
Q20	I often get briefed by my child's teachers	4.700	0.6569	94%

Figure 4: Dimension 4: Parenting Context**Table 4: Analysis & Interpretation of Involvement**

Involvement dimension contains totally 3 items (18-20), which discusses about the involvement of parents in raising their children. Item 18-20 have the extremely high percentage ranges between 91% to 94% which reveals that most of the parents are very much involved in their children's behaviour in terms of their academic and extracurricular activities and they also get brief understanding from their mentors about their behaviours.

Figure 5: Dimensions of Parenting Style based on NPP Questionnaire

Figure 5: A Bar diagram shows that Dimension 3 & 4, it reveals that there is a positive association between the Parental Context and Involvement with extremely significant and Dimension 1 & 2 are significant

Reliability: Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient

Alpha coefficient was developed by Lee Cronbach, to provide a measure of the internal consistency of a test or scale; it is expressed as a number between 0 and 1. Internal consistency describes the extent to which all the items in a test measure the same concept or construct and hence it is Internal consistency should be determined before a test can be employed for research or examination purposes to ensure validity (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). The Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient was calculated using,

$$\alpha = \frac{n}{n-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum v_i}{v_{test}} \right)$$

Where,

- n = number of questions
- v_i = variance of scores on each question
- v_{test} = total variance of overall scores (not %'s) on the entire test

Cronbach's alpha values were described as Excellent (>0.90), Good (0.80-0.89), Acceptable (0.70-0.79), Questionable (0.6-0.69), Poor (0.5-0.59) and Unacceptable (<0.59).

Table 5: Comparison of results related to subscales of internal consistency coefficients of Nicomachus-Positive Parenting Questionnaire Inter-Item Correlation Matrix.

Dimensions	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
1. Nurturing Values	0.739
2. Strength Identification & Boosting	0.727
3. Parenting Context	0.705
4. Involvement	0.679

The Nurturing Values, Strength Identification & Boosting, Parenting Context is "Acceptable" value as per Cronbach's alpha coefficient in Nicomachus-Positive Parenting Questionnaire and internal consistency coefficient of the factor Involvement have the lowest value which is "Questionable" in Nicomachus-Positive Parenting Questionnaire based on the values of Cronbach's alpha. Internal consistency coefficient is 0.856. According to this result, it is found to be relatively high and acceptable but the parental involvement was in a questionable state. Hence we have to take proper measures to look into the area though the percentage values are high.

Scale Validity

The subscales' internal consistency coefficients ranged from 0.67 to 0.73, it was determined that the subscales were consistently linked. This was considered as indication that the scale structure was valid.

Discussions

According to the findings, the test development and validation process were completed using four dimensions of Nicomachus-Positive Parenting Questionnaire. It was valid and reliable. It is determined to be extremely significant and there is a definite pattern of association between four dimensions: Nurturing Values, Strength Identification and Boosting, Parenting Context and Involvement had the acceptable Cronbach's alpha coefficient and questionable for the Involvement subscale. Because it is a critical tool for assessing how parents see their children's growth. The item analysis indicated that the scale had sufficient structural validity.

The present findings validate the study of parenting that may be an important force in shaping children's self-regulation and effortful control in early childhood but may have less of a role during pre-adolescence and adolescence. It is critical to understand the role of parenting in the development of self-regulation as this might point to a key mechanism of the effect of parenting on children's adjustment (Cowan, 2004).

Parenting style is an important factor in child development. Socio-emotional development of the child is influenced by the type of parenting style used in families. Parents, teachers and the mental health professionals must give more importance to the parenting styles and the society has to sort out steps to aware the parents regarding its importance (Joseph & John, 2008).

These findings related to parental control behaviours, the affective components of parenting, and parental responsiveness and sensitivity will be reported together. Careful attention was devoted to children's developmental stages, allowing for the identification of similarities or differences as children age (Kiff et al., 2011).

In concluding, Nicomachus-Positive Parenting Questionnaire is a feasible and trustworthy tool for parents of children aged 7 to 13 years, based on all of the above-mentioned findings. In Dimension 1, the parents need to improve themselves more in encouraging their children when they are emotionally down and bring them up towards the positive feeling by making them do the activities which they like the most, or by taking them to different places and allowing them for free play with their friends/siblings if they have. They also should stimulate them try out things repeatedly even if they did not succeed in past and always urge them to do the right thing even if there is no benefit out of it, which in turn help their children in balancing their emotions well. In Dimension 2, it states that most of parents are not allowing the children freely to study the related activity based on their strength out of their choice. They are forcing the children to satisfy their personal needs and branding their children for their own decisions, which in turns creates the negative effect on their parenting style. Due to this compulsion, children are affected both physically and mentally, also they tend to get depressed. In Dimension 3 & 4, it reveals that there is a positive association between the Parental Context and Involvement and it is highly significant.

The counselling to parents required based on these studies are that:

- To encourage the children to retry and attempt things, even though not successful in the past. Should be thought not be loose hope. Gaining new skills and attempt again.
- To do right thing even though there is no personal gain.
- To encourage the child to study and do related to his/her interest and strengths.

The emotional stability of the child should be increased. Child should be made to accept failure in good spirit. The parents expect that their child should be first in everything in all fields like in academic, sports and extracurricular activities. One need not train the child that they are good in one and bad in another. No need for the children to be good in everything.

Conclusions

This research was carried out to develop and validate a tool to measure perceived parental style using Nicomachus-Positive Parenting Questionnaire. The estimation of validity and reliability indicates that the present instrument is capable to measure parenting style of children of age 7 to 13. With the help of this instrument, it is found that Parental context and involvement is highly significant and propose a new pathway to further research in Nicomachus-Positive Parenting Questionnaire which includes the peer relationship, assertive discipline, constructive skills, generative skills, communicative skills can be assessed for improvement of the child development and the research can be extended to adolescents.

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Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Arias, M. B. (Arizona S. U., & Morillo-Campbell, M. (Arizona S. U. (2008). Promoting ELL Parental Involvement: Challenges in Contested Times. *Great Lakes Center for Education Research & Practice*, 480, 1–22. http://greatlakescenter.org/docs/Policy_Briefs/Arias_ELL.pdf
- Cowan, N. (2004). Working Memory Capacity, 14(3), 235. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10567-011-0093-4>. *Nature*
- Gafoor, A., & Kurukkan, A. (2014). Construction and Validation of Scale of Parenting Style. *Guru Journal of Behavioral and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 315–323.
- Jinnah, H. A., & Walters, L. H. (2003). ECRP . Vol 10 No 1 . Including Parents in Evaluation of a Child Development Program : Relevance of Parental Involvement ECRP . Vol 10 No 1 . Including Parents in Eva. 10(1), 1–7.
- Joseph, M. V., & John, J. (2008). Impact of Parenting Styles on Child Development. *Global Academic Society Journal: Social Science Insight*, 1(5), 16–25.
- Kiff, C. J., Lengua, L. J., & Zalewski, M. (2011). Nature and Nurturing: Parenting in the Context of Child Temperament. *Clinical Child and Family Psychology Review*, 14(3), 251–301. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10567-011-0093-4>
- Kyriazos, T. A., & Stalikas, A. (2019). Nicomachus-Positive Parenting (NPP): Development and Initial Validation of a Parenting Questionnaire within the Positive Psychology Framework. *Psychology*, 10(15), 2115–2165. <https://doi.org/10.4236/psych.2019.1015136>
- Maccoby, E. E. (2000). Parenting and its effects on children: On reading and misreading behavior genetics. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 51, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.51.1.1>
- Mohammad, A., Theodoros, K., Michalis, G., & Anastasios, S. (n.d.). A Parenting Model of Satisfaction-Dysfunctions to Evidence Construct Validity and Measurement Invariance of Kansas Parental Satisfaction Scale (KPSS), Greek Version.
- Önder, A., & Gülay, H. (2009). Reliability and validity of parenting styles & dimensions questionnaire. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 1(1), 508–514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2009.01.092>
- Rothbart, M. K., Ahadi, S. A., Hershey, K. L., & Fisher, P. (2001). Investigations of temperament at three to seven years: The children’s behavior questionnaire. *Child Development*, 72(5), 1394–1408. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00355>
- Shiner, R., & Caspi, A. (2003). Personality differences in childhood and adolescence: Measurement, development, and consequences. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry and Allied Disciplines*, 44(1), 2–32. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1469-7610.00101>
- Taber, K. S. (2018). The Use of Cronbach’s Alpha When Developing and Reporting Research Instruments in Science Education. *Research in Science Education*, 48(6), 1273–1296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-016-9602-2>
- Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach’s alpha. *International Journal of*

Medical Education, 2, 53–55. <https://doi.org/10.5116/ijme.4dfb.8dfd>

- Waters, L. (2015). The Relationship between Strength-Based Parenting with Children's Stress Levels and Strength-Based Coping Approaches. *Psychology*, 06(06), 689–699. <https://doi.org/10.4236/psych.2015.66067>

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